

foodpaths

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Revision history

Version	Date	Reviewer	Modifications
1 Final version	January	Hugo De Vries	Update of specific tools
2 Draft 2	December	Peter Defranceschi	Review of the tools
3 Draft 2	December	Hugo De Vries	Comment on the general structure
4 Draft 1	November	Anna Bruen	Comment on the general structure
5 Draft 1	November	Hugo De Vries	Comment on the general structure

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1. Glossary

- **Farm to Fork Strategy:** The Farm to Fork Strategy is part of the European Green Deal and it aims to accelerate our transition to a sustainable food system (website).
- **Governance:** The process, or the power, of governing; the specific system by which the Partnership is ruled,
- **Hub:** A physical or virtual space providing opportunities for knowledge sharing, networking, and exchange
- **Mirror Groups:** A group of individuals who provide input, feedback, reflections, and recommendations on an organisation/work being done. Working with mirror groups provides FOODPathS with an opportunity to learn about best governance and implementation practices and elevate the participants' voices and stories, including their priorities, reflections, and feedback, to ensure an inclusive, transparent partnership.
- **Participatory Processes:** refers to the active involvement of the people or the community in policy-formulation, project-planning or implementation (website).
- **Partnership:** an arrangement where parties agree to cooperate to advance their mutual interests,
- **Prototype:** An original form, or model (described in detail) which is the basis for the future Partnership,
- **Social inclusion:** Social inclusion is the process of improving the terms on which individuals and groups take part in society, improving the ability, opportunity, and dignity of those disadvantaged on the basis of their identity (website).
- **Sustainable Food Systems:** a sustainable food system provides and promotes safe, nutritious and healthy food of low environmental impact for all current and future EU citizens in a manner that itself also protects and restores the natural environment and its ecosystem services, is robust and resilient, economically dynamic, just and fair, and socially acceptable and inclusive (website).
- **Sustainable Food System Deals:** for the purpose of this paper safe and sustainable food system deals are initiatives, networks, partnerships, policy frameworks, and programs that have an overarching aim to transform the food system from a linear, extractive model, towards a circular and sustainable one. 'Deals' include more than one stakeholder and raise questions regarding benefits and trade-offs.
- **Systemic or Systems approach:** Within and affecting a whole system, with interacting actors and feedback loops.
- **Vulnerable groups:** Groups within our societies that face higher risk of poverty and social exclusion compared to the general population. These vulnerable and marginalised groups include but are not limited to: people with disabilities, migrants and ethnic minorities (including Roma), homeless people, ex-prisoners, drug addicts, people with alcohol problems, isolated older people and children (website).

Abbreviations

FS = Food Systems;

KPI = Key Performance Indicators;

RIPE = Research & Innovation & Science to Policy & Education;

SRIA = Strategic Research & innovation agenda;

SFS = Sustainable Food System(s)

2. Introduction

Inclusive partnerships play a crucial role in co-shaping food systems by influencing actors and their relationships. They help set direction, provide incentives, and create the foundation for an enabling environment. To build a **successful and inclusive food systems partnership**, it's not enough to just bring people together to tackle food system challenges. There is a need for a clear plan that creates an open and lively space where different voices can share their ideas and make a real difference. Based on the premise that inclusive partnerships are a key driver of food systems transformation, this toolkit **offers practical guidance** for creating such an environment and enabling effective partnerships. It provides practical instruments to address the challenges related to inclusivity while creating opportunities to reduce trade-offs and maximize co-benefits when adopting a food systems approach. The **toolkit is accessible and adaptable** across diverse contexts and governance scales, ensuring its relevance to a wide range of applications.

The toolkit includes a carefully selected number of best practices and a variety of resources such as templates and worksheets, checklists, workshop materials and recommendations.

Overview of the Tools:

Tool 1 – Strategic guidelines for partnership

Tool 2 – RIPE concept

Tool 3 – Guidelines for Mirror Groups

Tool 4 – Guidelines and Recommendations for Calls

Tool 5 – Game structure and methodology

Tool 6 – Mapping funders

Tool 7 – Mapping Research organizations

Tool 8 – Case study mapping and analysis

Tool 9 – Feedback Survey

Tool 10 – Communication outcome

Tool 11 – Co-construction and liaison ambition of multiple networks at all scales

3. What you will find in this toolkit

Drawing from key interventions and lessons learned from the FOODPathS project, this toolkit aims to provide pragmatic tools to amplify the potential of such partnerships. This toolkit is organized to cover **four key areas** that include inclusive partnership models, strategies for mapping and engaging funders, strategies for mapping and engaging research and education- establishing living labs, and communication and dissemination

For each area, the document provides **essential concepts and practical tools** designed to help maximize benefits and reduce trade-offs. This toolkit should be viewed as a flexible toolkit to experiment, learn, and adapted to specific needs and context. There is no set sequence nor specific rules to follow. To ensure different levels of detail, we have structured a first section dedicated to tools, where you will find each tool

along with a brief description of its objectives, target audience, and content. The document concludes with annexes providing complete forms and reference documents for further exploration.

4. Who is the toolkit for

This toolkit is designed for use by FutureFoodS, the European partnership on sustainable food systems which includes the European Commission, EU member states, and various key stakeholders. It is envisaged that the partnership will collectively invest in research and innovation to transform food systems. The toolkit aims to support these efforts and to achieve the sustainability goals outlined in the EU Farm-to-Fork Strategy and the European Green Deal.

5. Approach and tools

Category	Description	List of tools
Concept Tools	The main objective of this category is to support public, private and research organizations in the development of inclusive SFS. The list of tools provides a useful concept/roadmap for the development and support of SFS transformation that is both inclusive and sustainable.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tool 1 – Strategic guidelines for partnership • Tool 2 – RIPE concept • Tool 3 – Guidelines and Recommendations for calls
Mapping tools	The main objective of this category is to provide structured and practical forms/indications to collect and analyse key studies and best practices that are effectively supporting the transformation towards inclusive, of safe and sustainable food systems. Besides that, some tools provide a visual representation of key stakeholders active in Europe.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tool 4 – Game structure and methodology • Tool 5 – Mapping funders • Tool 6 – Mapping Research organizations • Tool 7 – Case study mapping and analysis
Engagement tools	The main objective of this category is to provide useful support for communication activities to collect feedback as well as run effective workshops.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tool 8 – Guidelines for Mirror Groups • Tool 9 – Feedback Survey • Tool 10 – Communication outcome • Tool 11 – Co-construction and liaison ambition of multiple networks at all scales

6. Tools for Inclusive SFS Partnerships

An overall description of each tool can be found in the following pages. More information and details about each tool can be found in the Appendix.

6.1 Tool 1: A strategic guideline for inclusive partnerships

Collaboration is essential to address food systems sustainability challenges, but... how can you establish a Partnership in Food Systems? This poses numerous other questions like which complex societal challenges do you collectively tackle? How do you monitor them and translate them into joint actions? Which approaches would you then like to follow? Which shared principles do you follow? How do you utilize existing and forthcoming knowledge and experiences? How do you avoid trade-offs and seek co-benefits?

FOODPathS is proposing the guiding concept of a “bird” for a Partnership. By forming a flock of birds – representing other Partnerships and large-scale initiatives – they can face the challenges and accelerate the transition toward SFS

A strategic guideline for a Partnership

Category/identifier	Concept tool
Name	A strategic guideline for a Partnership
Type	Facilitation methodology
Description:	The image of a flock of birds is used to describe how societal challenges can be confronted by a group of partnerships capable of observing, learning and adapting their courses to reach sustainability.
Aim	Aim 1: Describing a set of key features of Partnerships that allow navigating towards sustainable food system outcomes Aim 2: Forming flocks with other Partnerships to tackle complex societal challenges
URL reference	The URL is forthcoming. Based on: Hugo de Vries. Food for thought - Coupling between 'licence to produce' and 'licence to explore'. <i>Technology & Services</i> , 2002. (hal-02934667)
Associated deliverable/milestone	FOODPathS Deliverable D2.3 ' Manual Prototype Partnership 1.0 ' Weblink: forthcoming
From the deliverable report, workshops, and executed tasks to the tool description.	The FOODPathS “bird” strategic guideline is composed of 8 key elements, that all needs to be specified by a future Partnership: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <u>Define the vision & the expected sustainable value created</u>; this addresses sustainability consequently from the three dimensions (environmental, social, and economic) 2. <u>Specify the governance and legal status of a partnership</u>; this incorporates balanced bottom-up and top-down decision-making processes, cross-scales and multi-stakeholder group interactions, and flexibility as well as adaptability in structures and functions. 3. <u>Explicit the <i>Modus operandi</i></u>; this preferentially favors collective intelligence and systemic approaches in all operations including human resources, finance, communication, etc.

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. <u>Revisit activity areas (SRIA¹) by connecting R&I with Policies and Education (RIPE) programs;</u> here, it is recommended connecting thematic areas via a Food Systems Lens thanks to transversal actions like Food System Labs, (University) Networks and a sustainability chart. 5. <u>Formulate co-funding mechanisms & a funders forum;</u> the alignment of funding strategies and priorities of diverse funders is an essential transversal action to carry out R&I activities that follow food system approaches. 6. <u>List potential trade-offs and co-benefits;</u> whatever a Partnership undertakes, trade-offs and co-benefits are inevitable; hence ,feedback from Observatories, Mirror Groups, transition needs of various actor groups, inter-continental conflicting issues, and other ways of knowledge generation (e.g. indigenous knowledge) are suggested to be taken into account. 7. <u>Develop a consistent communication, dissemination & exploitation (CDE) plan;</u> CDE actions are intended to generate a snowball effect that motivates numerous other FS actors to join forces to reach sustainability outcomes. 8. <u>Elaborate Cooperations with other partnerships and large initiatives;</u> outcomes cannot be reached by a single Partnerships, because issues are far too complex. 9.
Target	Any food system actor from public, private, academic, philanthropic, or non-governmental sectors that is willing to join partnerships on sustainable food systems
Type of tool	1 pager + 1 image (next page)
Exploitability	At any workshop

Figure 1 The key elements of the prototype Partnership, presented as a bird, forming a flock with other Partnerships and large scale initiatives to accelerate the transition towards SFS. Communication is then primordial; Modified design from H. Schepers & H. de Vries; ([hal-02934667](https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-02934667))

¹ https://scar-europe.org/images/FOOD/Main_actions/SFS_Partnership_SRIA_31012023.pdf

6.2 Tool 2: the RIPE Concept

Introduction: The RIPE concept tool connects Research & Innovation (R&I), Policy (P), and Education (E) to foster sustainable food systems partnerships. Its methodology evolves from siloed themes to integrated approaches, aligning R&I, P, and E priorities. It identifies key themes and synergies from strategic agendas, offering practical guidelines for case studies, funding calls, and collaboration networks. The tool targets actors from public, private, academic, and non-governmental sectors interested in advancing sustainable food systems.

The RIPE concept

Category/identifier	Concept tool
Name	The RIPE concept connecting research, innovation, policy and education to sustainably evolving food systems partnerships.
Type	Facilitation methodology
Description:	The image of four separated silos for R&I, P, and E (Figure 1) evolves towards an image in which R&I, P and E converge to reach sustainable evolving food systems partnerships (Figure 2).
Aim	Aim 1: align Research & Innovation (R&I), science-to-Policy (P) and Education (E) themes that are relevant for Partnerships on Sustainable Food Systems (SFS), Figure 1 ; Aim 2: design a concept for SFS that allows integrally reflecting on cross RIPE priorities,'D6.2).
URL reference	The URL is forthcoming.
Associated deliverable/milestone	FOODPathS Deliverable D6.2 'The RIPE concept ' Weblinks: www.FOODPathS.eu for all deliverable reports mentioned here and the SRIA of the P-SFS at the SCAR (2023) https://scar-europe.org/images/FOOD/Main_actions/SFS_Partnership_SRIA_31012023.pdf
From the deliverable report, workshops, and executed tasks to the tool description.	The main steps to be taken are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extract the key <u>R&I themes</u> from the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of the P-SFS (SCAR, 2023) • List the major <u>science-to-Policy topics</u> from FOODPathS Deliverable 6.1 and from the Ghent-group discussions. • Collect the main <u>Education priorities</u> from FOODPathS Deliverable 5.1 and from the Pact4Skills-related initiatives. • <u>Cross-check R&I themes, P topics, and E priorities</u> to seek synergies, gaps and critical issues. Define potential strategies for these synergies, solutions for gaps, and alternative approaches for critical issues, taking into account the concept that connects RIPE with sustainably evolving food systems partnerships (for more details, see D6.2) • <u>Translate the strategies, solutions and approaches into practical guidelines for:</u> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> (i) executing and demonstrating case studies via the Knowledge Hub of Food Systems Labs (D2.1 and D4.2) (ii) utilizing effectively the food system observatory for sustainability aims (D2.2 & D2.4) (iii) aligning funding calls of Partnership(s) (D3.2) (iv) structuring a branded network of universities (D5.2)
Target	Any food system actor from public, private, academic, philanthropic, or non-governmental sectors that is willing to join partnerships (and large initiatives) on sustainable food systems, both in R&I, as well as in Education and Policymaking.
Type of tool	1 pager + 1 image (next page)
Exploitability	At any workshop

Figure 2 Research and Innovation (R&I), science-to-Policy (P) and Education (ED)

6.3 Tool 3: Call & Funding Analysis

Introduction: The following recommendations aim to provide guidance when developing funding opportunities (calls or grants) dedicated to supporting Sustainable Food Systems (SFS). They outline - based on the experience of various stakeholders involved in this field - the essential elements that must be included in a call to support the spread of inclusive SFS.

This tool is therefore intended for all those engaged in supporting SFS, both public and private actors, who aim to generate impact and contribute to transforming food systems towards greater sustainability for people and the environment.

Our first target is the FutureFoodS Partnership, but we assume that all actors interested in funding SFS could try inspiration from these recommendations.

It should be noted that they are the result of the analysis of 21 calls, which includes calls from ERA-nets, HEU Partnerships, regional calls, HEU Framework Programme and Foundations. The analysis focused on how a food systems approach (FSA) can be implemented into future call mechanisms.

Category/identifier	Guidelines and Recommendation tool
Name	Recommendation to develop granting schemes/calls supporting inclusive SFS
Type	recommendations
Description:	This tool is meant to support private and public organizations aiming to develop granting schemes or calls to support SFS transformation. It includes a short series of recommendations that need to be considered if the aim is to support the transition towards a more safe and sustainable food system.
Aim	Aim: provide useful indications and create an agreement around funding schemes dedicated to SFS
URL reference	The URL is forthcoming.
Associated deliverable/milestone	

<p>From the deliverable report, workshops, and executed tasks to the tool description.</p>	<p>Main recommendations to develop a call on SFS:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Provide a definition of systems approach or a clear explanation of what is meant; 2. Be mindful and consistent with terminology, e.g. when using typical elements of a systems approach such as multi-/inter-/transdisciplinarity; 3. Cross-disciplinarity, stakeholder engagement, and multi-actor approach are highly demanded and also of great relevance for a systems approach call; think about where and how to ask for these aspects and consider the differences between the concepts; 4. When applying a systems approach it is important to consider both synergies and trade-offs; 5. Think about how impact shall be achieved by the projects, how the food systems approach contributes to impact and provides guidance and support towards applicants; 6. What additions to the proposals are sensible and what shall they contain (e.g. impact plan, DEC plan, stakeholder engagement plan, implementation/valorisation plan, etc.); adapt to the systems approach and consider also follow-up and adjustments over time (revisiting the plan); 7. Networking activities facilitated at programme level can be valuable to align and/or collaborate with other projects or programmes but they need to be backed up with dedicated resources (they might even be a necessity for co-design and co-creation); 8. Be open to new funding instruments beyond classical projects (e.g. knowledge hubs) to create mechanisms for fostering connectivity, co-creation and inclusiveness.
<p>Target</p>	<p>Private and public funder organizations</p>
<p>Type of tool</p>	<p>One pager and figure</p>
<p>Exploitability</p>	<p>The tool could be used by the EU Commission, Future FoodS Partnership and any other grant-making organization supporting SFS transformation.</p>

RECOMMENDATIONS:

1. Provide a definition of systems approach or a clear explanation of what is meant;
2. Be mindful and consistent with terminology, e.g. when using typical elements of a systems approach such as multi-/inter-/transdisciplinarity;
3. Cross-disciplinarity, stakeholder engagement, and multi-actor approach are highly demanded and also of great relevance for a systems approach call; think about where and how to ask for these aspects and consider the differences between the concepts;
4. When applying a systems approach it is important to consider both synergies and trade-offs;
5. Think about how impact shall be achieved by the projects, how the food systems approach contributes to impact and provides guidance and support towards applicants;
6. What additions to the proposals are sensible and what shall they contain (e.g. impact plan, DEC plan, stakeholder engagement plan, implementation/valorisation plan etc.); adapt to the systems approach and consider also follow-up and adjustments over time (revisiting the plan);
7. Networking activities facilitated at programme level can be valuable to align and/or collaborate with other projects or programmes but they need to be backed up with dedicated resources (they might even be a necessity for co-design and co-creation);
8. Be open to new funding instruments beyond classical projects (e.g. knowledge hubs) to create mechanisms for fostering connectivity, co-creation and inclusiveness.

Fig 4. List of recommendations to develop granting schemes/calls supporting inclusive SFS

6.4 Tool 4: Case Studies Development

Introduction: This tool is designed to support the mapping of case studies within food systems, enabling the identification of best practices and avoiding the repetition of previous efforts. The tool provides a structured template, inspired by a GAME framework (de Vries et al., 2022²), to analyze key aspects of each case study. It includes essential elements such as the case's history, main characteristics, actor interactions, and sustainability outcomes. The template also explores the dynamics of collaboration, governance evolution, and the external inputs and outputs of the involved actors. By using this template, stakeholders can gain valuable insights into the functioning and impact of food system cases, facilitating better decision-making and fostering innovation in food system partnerships.

Category/identifier	Mapping tool
Name	Food System Game structure methodology
Type	Facilitation methodology
Description:	The food system game structure methodology is a methodology that can be used by diverse actors to describe a food system case using a similar template. Each case has a playing field (context), players (food system actors), pieces (resources), moves (activities), rules (boundaries, laws,..), time (timing of activities), and outcomes (sustainable or unsustainable).
Aim	Aim 1: Describing a set of food system cases in a similar way, allowing comparing results and exchanging insights. Aim 2: Being inclusive, because all people are familiar with the structure of a game in their daily life.
URL reference	-De Vries, H., Donner, M. & Axelos, M. (2022). Sustainable food systems science based on physics principles. <i>Trends in Food Science and Technology</i> , Elsevier, 2022, 123, pp.382-392. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2022.03.027 (original ^version) - de Vries H, Donner M, Fabiano F, Mamès M, Lazaro-Mojica J, Cotillas E, Avila C, Martínez J, Alcat G, Rossi D, Pierantoni E, Marini T, Bruen A, Vordemfelde J, Amorese V, Liroši L and Voyatzakis A (2024) Co-creation in partnerships contributing to the sustainability of food systems: insights from 52 case studies in Europe. <i>Front. Sustain. Food Syst.</i> 8:1399275. https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2024.1399275 - De Vries, H.; Donner, M.; Fabiano, F. and Mamès, M. (2024) A new methodology for collaborative business models in the transition towards sustainable food systems. In: <i>Routledge Handbook of Agribusiness</i> ; Editors Alessio Cavicchi, Domenico Dentoni, and Gianluca Brunori. Accepted for publication.
Associated deliverable/milestone	FOODPathS Deliverable D2.1 https://www.FOODPathS.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/Deliverable-2.1-Mapping-results-fv_compressed.pdf https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5fafa60f4&applied=PPGMS
From the deliverable report,	Since food is our first primary need, it is not amazing that the food sector is the largest in Europe in terms of employment and diversity of actors. However, how can these actors

² De Vries, H., Donner, M. & Axelos, M. (2022). Sustainable food systems science based on physics principles. *Trends in Food Science and Technology*, Elsevier, 2022, 123, pp.382-392. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2022.03.027>
- de Vries H, Donner M, Fabiano F, Mamès M, Lazaro-Mojica J, Cotillas E, Avila C, Martínez J, Alcat G, Rossi D, Pierantoni E, Marini T, Bruen A, Vordemfelde J, Amorese V, Liroši L and Voyatzakis A (2024) Co-creation in partnerships contributing to the sustainability of food systems: insights from 52 case studies in Europe. *Front. Sustain. Food Syst.* 8:1399275. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2024.1399275>.

workshops, and executed tasks to the tool description.	<p>guarantee the provision of food for all, everywhere and anytime, hence also for all our future generations?</p> <p>Numerous initiatives have been launched by different configurations of actors, at different scales, that are striving for contributions to the sustainability of our food systems. But how are they functioning and structured? How can they be exemplary for others in other contexts? How can you become involved and have an added value? These and other questions can only be addressed if food system cases are described in a comprehensible and attractive manner for all actors.</p> <p>That is the reason that the structure of a game is chosen and translated into a template that actors can use to present the case and discuss content and objectives with others.</p>
Target	Any food system actor from public, private, academic, philanthropic, or non-governmental sectors
Type of tool	Template
Exploitability	At any workshop

6.5 Tool 5: Mapping & Engaging Partners

Introduction: The following map represents an illustrative exercise that has been developed to give basic information about the actors/funders interested funders to support SFS in the EU context. Being part of the map is not associated with any formal commitment and is completely voluntary.

Despite this, it is believed that for any stakeholder interested in supporting or participating in the construction of an SFS, it could be helpful to have an idea of the most active actors in Europe on this topic.

For this reason, we consider this tool to be extremely informative both for those seeking funding and for the stakeholders contributing with their financing to the development of SFS, who wish to join the European network of active participants in this field.

Please note that the complete and interactive funders map can be found on the FOODPathS homepage (<https://www.FOODPathS.eu/map-of-funders/>) and is summarized as follows in Fig. 1.

Category/identifier	Mapping tool
Name	Map of funders
Type	Illustration/Visual image
Description:	The aim of the funders network and map is to gather and showcase a group of interested funders who are willing to support SFS transformation.
Aim	1. Aim: visualize funder organizations in Europe that support Food System Transformation
URL reference	https://www.FOODPathS.eu/map-of-funders/
Associated deliverable/milestone	Del. 3.1 Report on funders' engagement and Funders Forum agenda
From the deliverable report, workshops, and executed tasks to the tool description.	<p>The main steps to develop the Funders Map include:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <u>Define the methodology for the map</u>: The mapping methodology involved engaging funders through surveys and dialogues to build a network and map of public and private co-funders for sustainable food systems. This was done in four waves, contacting networks, advisory boards, and other stakeholders. Funders provided organizational details and their priorities across four R&I areas: nutrition and health, production and supply, citizen participation, and governance. The survey collected insights to align funding strategies with the objectives of the SRIA for the future partnership. 2. <u>The main results</u>: A total of 40 funding organizations from 19 countries joined the FOODPathS Funders Network, with 37 agreeing to be featured on the Funders Map. Most organizations were governmental, with significant engagement from countries like Belgium, Finland, and Italy, while others like Austria and Bulgaria were unrepresented. The "production, processing, and supply" R&I area received the highest priority from funders, followed by "nutrition and health," both rated as high or medium priority by all respondents. In contrast, "consumer involvement and citizen participation" and "politics, policies, and governance of food systems" had mixed feedback, with some organizations rating these areas as low or no priority. Overall, the majority of funders expressed medium or high interest in all four R&I areas, though prioritization varied. 3. <u>Develop an interactive map</u>: translate the results into an interactive and visual image.
Target	Two main targets: on the one hand anyone seeking funding on SFS and on the other hand stakeholders contributing with their financing to the development of SFS.

Type of tool	image
Exploitability	To represent funding resources in Europe at workshops or for research

<https://www.FOODPathS.eu/map-of-funders/>

Fig 5. Map of funders of SFS in Europe

6.6 Tool 6: Engaging Research & Education

Introduction: Education and research institutions, from elementary schools to universities, are pivotal in advancing sustainable food systems (SFS). Higher education institutions, particularly those focused on sustainability, drive innovation through research that shapes policies, practices, and technologies. To foster effective partnerships, the approach involves mapping active institutions, understanding their roles, and bridging education with community needs.

Key steps include identifying institutions engaged in SFS, conducting workshops to clarify roles and barriers, and promoting a balance between theoretical knowledge and practical applications through fieldwork and partnerships. Strengthening ties with community initiatives ensures that educational efforts remain relevant, while universities can amplify these efforts through research, service learning, and policy advocacy.

In the following, it is possible to find which are, according to FOODPathS experience, the key steps to effectively map those institutions.

Interested actors could use the following as a practical list of actions to carry out their mapping exercise. Please note that these suggestions could be adapted, with the necessary cautions, also to other mapping activities.

Category/identifier	Mapping tool
Name	Mapping research and education on SFS
Type	Mapping methodology/form
Description:	The key steps to effectively map and engage research and education institutions in the development of open and inclusive food system partnership
Aim	Aim: provide support to Future Foods Partnership on how to engage education and research institutions
URL reference	
Associated deliverable/milestone	
From the deliverable report, workshops, and executed tasks to the tool description.	<p>The tool focuses on the main steps to engage research and education organizations including:</p> <p>Step 1: Mapping and identifying active institutions (education, research, and practice) according to their engagement level, focus on sustainability, and areas of expertise. Create a database of educational institutions from kindergarten to universities engaged in food systems work and classify them according to their focus areas and sustainability priorities. Conclude this step by conducting a series of interviews with key representatives.</p> <p>Step 2: Open the debate to institutions by conducting workshops to understand the various roles and responsibilities of different institutions</p> <p>Step 3: Balance theory and practice Encourage universities to develop food systems courses that blend theory with fieldwork, internships, and service learning. These can include partnerships with local food organizations, urban farms, or government agencies.</p> <p>Step 4: Advocate for a more inclusive SFS that strengthens the connection between educational institutions and community initiatives.</p>
Target	Research institutions, policy officers, private-public organizations, and Future FoodS Partnership
Type of tool	One pager
Exploitability	The tool could be used by the EU Commission, Future FoodS Partnership, private and public organizations and other EU projects.

6.7 Tool 7: Guidelines for organizing and facilitating mirror groups

Introduction: Project consortia and partnerships are not able to include all the diverse voices and perspectives needed to transform our food systems in a just and inclusive manner. They are often constrained by time, funding, or a limit on the number of organizations that can participate. Mirror groups bring relevant additional organizations and stakeholder groups to the discussion table and their ideas into decision-making processes. They help ensure that the transition to a sustainable food system is participatory, inclusive, and responsive to various actors' needs and inputs. These guidelines introduce key concepts, methods, and attitudes needed to establish and facilitate mirror groups. It provides a roadmap, but importantly it needs to be adapted to fit specific contexts and needs.

Category/identifier	Guidelines and Recommendation tool
Name	Guidelines for organizing mirror groups
Type	Facilitation methodology
Description:	The concept of Mirror Groups enhances the development of an inclusive food system taking into account views and positions from all diverse perspectives.
Aim	Aim 1: include perspectives that are normally missed Aim 2: Share ideas Aim 3: reconcile different perspectives
URL reference	https://sites.inrae.fr/site/FOODPathS/_layouts/15/WopiFrame.aspx?source doc=%7B0828952D-BED9-47BD-A4FD-94A5DD5F6C11%7D&file=Final%20for%20V1_FOODPathS_MirrorGroups Guidelines_comments_DK_FR_AT_PD.docx&action=default&lsList=1 &ListId=%7B13990D36-3B9E-4C59-AB58-3DD9C7539346%7D&ListItemId=2547
Associated deliverable/milestone	D???
From the deliverable report, workshops, and executed tasks to the tool description.	<p>The main elements of the strategic guidelines are:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) <u>Definition of what is a Mirror Group.</u> There is no precise definition about what is a mirror group however, there is largely shared a common understanding of mirror groups as groups of actors that bring together different kinds of organizations and initiatives that are not directly involved, but may be impacted by it and/or have valuable related experience to contribute. 2) <u>Clarification on the use/purpose of Mirror Groups.</u> Mirror groups are useful for including perspectives, recognizing and reconciling different organizational backgrounds and agendas, understanding how to collaborate effectively, sharing ideas, and agreeing on a common basis. 3) <u>Develop the Mirror Groups – the main steps to follow</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Identify a person or 2 dedicated to setting up mirror groups ● Develop a concept note ● Clearly set objectives and a timeline for each meeting ● Develop a list of relevant participants, select and invite the participants ● Brief the participants ● Document the meeting ● Follow up participants <p>Key suggestions when developing a mirror group</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Engage the project/partners since the very beginning (concept note definition)• Clarify Roles and Responsibilities• Establish a Safer* Space• Manage time effectively during the meeting to ensure all topics are covered and discussions are productive.• Share the outcomes with all participants and stakeholders to ensure transparency and continuous improvement.
Target	All actors/stakeholders/organizations engaged in the development of SFS.
Type of tool	1 pager
Exploitability	Any project on SFS and beyond that aims to be inclusive and open.

6.8 Tool 8: Mapping Results

Introduction: This tool is designed to support the future partnership on Sustainable Food Systems (SFS) and other stakeholders in identifying best practices for SFS development. It provides a structured approach to analyze case studies, focusing on their evolution, governance, and sustainability while highlighting opportunities for scalability. Key recommendations address diverse stakeholder needs, from funding strategies to fostering collaborations between private, public, and academic sectors.

Category/identifier	Mapping tool
Name	Case study/best practices collection
Type	Mapping methodology/form
Description:	Support the identification and analysis of key case studies.
Aim	Aim: provide a structured approach to map best practices on SFS
URL reference	The URL is forthcoming.
Associated deliverable/milestone	
From the deliverable report, workshops, and executed tasks to the tool description.	<p>A structured approach to case study selection:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Define the selection criteria making sure cases cover the Strategic Research Agenda (SRIA) four Research and Innovation (R&I) and Activity Areas and Prioritize cases, geographic diversity, stakeholder groups, activities, enabling factors, and sustainability dimensions. 2. Select a limited number of key studies to allow an in-depth analysis of each case and cover history and evolution, how Food System (FS) approaches are implemented, scalability and applicability, key trends, governance models, network functioning, value creation in partnerships, sustainability indicators, and trade-offs in food systems. 3. Summarize the results in clear recommendations differentiated for stakeholder groups (funders, private Sector academia and public sector)
Target	Food Future FoodS Partnership, EU projects and researchers and academics, policy officers
Type of tool	One pager
Exploitability	Any EU-funded projects, Workshops and Research projects

6.9 Tool 9: Feedback Collection

Introduction: This tool draws on the insights from the "Feedback from Society" report within the FOODPathS project, which analyzes responses from an online survey conducted among local, national, and European stakeholders in the EU food systems. It provides a detailed understanding of the roles stakeholders can play in partnerships, the types of activities they are keen to engage in, and their preferred communication channels for outreach.

Category/identifier	Communication tool
Name	Survey for collecting stakeholders' perspectives
Type	Survey template
Description:	Partnerships should be built by including all the voices of actors potentially interested. For this reason, consultive methods should be put in place. In FOODPathS, we have delivered a survey to understand the opinion of stakeholders' representatives on how an ideal partnership for sustainable food systems should look. Results were analysed and enabled the consortium to formulate recommendations and best practices that might be adopted by FutureFoodS or other partnerships working in food systems sustainability.
Aim	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collect opinions of stakeholders - Formulate recommendations for stakeholders
URL reference	Upcoming
Associated deliverable/milestone	D8.3 Feedback from society
From the deliverable report, workshops, and executed tasks to the tool description.	<p>The tool consists of a template for a survey, that could inspire other stakeholders interested in exploring and assessing food systems actors on how to work together and establish a partnership to tackle the challenge of sustainability and transformation.</p> <p>On the other hand, the results of the FOODPathS survey constitute a precious tool for European Partnerships (i.e., FutureFoodS, PRIMA, EIT Food, etc.), as well as for other similar initiatives, operating at local, regional, national and international levels. In particular, the main element of interest is represented by recommendations and action points.</p> <p>Lessons learned on building a Partnership SFS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Partnership definition and meaning: The survey defined a context where, besides the R&I Partnerships of the EC (FutureFoodS, Agroecology Partnership, etc.), stakeholders are working together to transform the European food systems through living labs, policy councils, EU-funded R&I projects and many more initiatives. They cannot be excluded from the "partnership" definition because not falling in the description provided by the EC: on the contrary, they should be considered as "a different level of partnership", that should dialogue and interact with the institutionalised initiatives of the EC. In this context, FOODPathS can play the role of connecting this different level of partnerships with the formal ones built by the EC. - Collaboration is the most relevant benefit of working in a partnership: an ideal partnership requires a good collaborative environment, that, together with the provision of a funding mechanism, prioritise the openness of participation. - A minor role for public and private investors in a partnership: There is a scarce consideration for these actors in contrast with the concept of

	<p>inclusivity. Moreover, it could raise doubts about the collaborative spirit of such a partnership.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A wide range of stakeholders are willing to support with their (different) expertise: there is a wide range of voices outside the SFS Partnership that want to participate somehow in the food systems transformation. However, considering the limitations that the R&I Partnership set by the EC could have (in terms of participation rules, organisational limitations – i.e., the number of people that could be involved in a SAB –, resources, etc.) it is important to not waste this knowledge and commitment. In this context, FOODPathS could keep playing the role of the collector of such voices and the bridge with the SFS Partnership, even after the end of the project. <p><i>Recommendations for FutureFoodS</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure transparency and openness to stimulate the participation in the partnership: this could be addressed by improving communication about the partnership scopes and activities, also providing more information about its funding mechanisms, how to contribute, etc. • Increasing opportunities for stakeholders to contribute to the partnership work: FutureFoodS could clarify and promote what are the “entry points” for food systems actors to provide their feedback and ideas, establishing a structured and continuous dialogue. • Reduce the burden for participation: another obstacle to the stakeholders’ participation is constituted by the lack of resources. Even if this is not an issue entirely in the hands of the partnership, maybe it would be worth exploring if there are any other ways to work together with food systems actors and/or make a more effective use of resources to ease their participation. <p>Communication activities to increase awareness on FutureFoodS and its impacts: among communication activities suggested, respondents proposed to run social media campaigns. This could allow FutureFoodS to reach a wider audience and inform them about the scope of the initiatives carried out and the long-term impact it could generate in society.</p>
Target	Partnerships, policymakers, representatives of food systems actors
Type of tool	Template, document and factsheet
Exploitability	FutureFoodS and other partnerships, policymakers

With this data-driven approach, the feedback collection tool empowers users to:

- Identify priorities for establishing inclusive and impactful partnerships.
- Understand stakeholder expectations and areas of interest.
- Design communication strategies tailored to diverse audiences.

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6.10 Tool 10: Communicating Outcomes

Category/identifier	Communication tool
Name	Communication materials for food systems sustainability
Type	a set of different communication tools
Description:	Collection of communication activities developed by FOODPathS to communicate about food systems topics with a wide range of stakeholders
Aim	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Raise awareness on food systems sustainability topic - Share knowledge among food systems actors <p>Stimulate the debate around food systems topics</p>
URL reference	To be added
Associated deliverable/milestone	D8.1
From the deliverable report, workshops, and executed tasks to the tool description.	<p>This tool is composed of different items addressing the need to communicate about food systems sustainability with variegated typologies of stakeholders. They are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - FOODPathS webinars: organised in collaboration with other projects and with the involvement of experts to discuss crucial points of the food systems sustainability, i.e., how to include both health and sustainability aspects in research, Artificial Intelligence and food systems sustainability, the educational system to boost food systems transformation, etc. - FOODCastS: a series of podcast episodes realized by the project to collect points of view and opinions from external experts on food systems topics. <p>Leaflets: a collection of visual materials to provide more information on the project and on some of its activities and results (i.e., on inclusiveness in food systems sustainability, funders, etc.).</p>
Target	All food systems actors (each item has its own identified target)
Type of tool	Videos, podcasts, visuals
Exploitability	Promotion among food systems actors

Podcasts, webinars, website, case studies

6.11 Tool 11: CO-CONSTRUCTION AND LIAISON AMBITION OF MULTIPLE NETWORKS AT ALL SCALES

Category/identifier	Communication tool
Name	CO-CONSTRUCTION AND LIAISON AMBITION OF MULTIPLE NETWORKS AT ALL SCALES
Type	Report format
Description:	This document was developed as a <i>living</i> document to support reflections of different actors to systematize key learnings and knowledge gathered throughout one or more events and workshops.
Aim	Foster inclusivity and support SFS transformation
URL reference	TO be indicated
Associated deliverable/milestone	MS13
From the deliverable report, workshops, and executed tasks to the tool description.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Data Collection format should include at least the workshop title, workshop format (including format), target audience and a summary of the outcomes and next steps. 2. Analysis of the Results. After each event make sure to use the document to analyse the main findings and outputs. 3. Conclusions. Use this section to summarize the main results gathered throughout the event[s]. If the document is used to support only one workshop conclusions will be used to elicit a reflection over what are the main and shared ambitions. In the case of using the document to support more than one workshop, conclusions will be progressively enriched as the workshops unfold, ensuring an open and inclusive approach.
Target	Public and private institutions/organizations, Future FoodS partnership, policy officers, academia and research organizations
Type of tool	One pager
Exploitability	Any EU-funded projects, workshops and research projects

Annexes

TOOL 1: Recommendations for inclusive partnerships

Step 1: Mapping: Identifying existing networks and their best practices

The first step in building an inclusive partnership is understanding the existing landscape. This involves identifying key actors, networks, and platforms that are already working on food system issues. Focus on mapping both the problems (e.g., unsafe or unsustainable food practices) and the solutions (e.g., successful collaborations, voluntary agreements, or policies).

- Identify critical issues and successful practices within food systems
- Consider diversity within networks. The most successful partnerships often include a broad range of stakeholders, such as city officials, farmers, businesses, NGOs, and citizens. Ensure that your mapping process captures this diversity.

Tip: In the case of the FOODPathS project, we identified a range of existing networks, platforms and partnerships. Several cases mapped were directly related to networks focusing on food policies (Milan Food Policy, New York Food Policy, Berlin Food Council) and cases of collaboration between civil society and municipalities.

Step 2: Conduct Interviews: engage a balanced range of stakeholders

After mapping, analyse the best practices identified and engage stakeholders directly through interviews to learn about roadblocks and opportunities for including, meaningful input from diverse voices in food systems. Choose interviewees from different scales of action (local, regional, national, global), areas of focus, and geographic locations to get a comprehensive view of the food system.

- Gain insights into governance and implementation practices, identify best practices, and uncover potential collaborators.
- Develop a standard set of questions to guide your interviews, and select a representative range of stakeholders, including governments, global organizations, and grassroots initiatives.

Tip: Clearly define the goals of the interviews to ensure that you're gathering relevant, actionable information. In FOODPathS we gave thought into our ways of communicating (methods, mediums, scales) and make language universally understandable and relevant.

Step 3: Develop key performance indicators (KPIs): Set success criteria early

Before moving forward with mapping or interviews, it's essential to define what success looks like. Set clear targets, such as the number of organizations to map, the diversity of interviewees, or specific issues you want to address through the interviews.

- Establish measurable criteria to track progress and ensure all relevant issues are being addressed.

Tip: these KPIs should help you stay on track and adapt your approach if needed

Step 4: Analyse interview results: identify themes and gaps

Once the interviews are completed, analyse the results by looking for recurring themes. Consider how these align with the issues identified during the mapping stage. In FOODPathS common themes identified included sustainability definitions, governance structures, or methodologies for driving change.

- Use the results to identify gaps, governance models, and best practices that can guide future partnerships.

Tip: it is important to realise that the responsibility for change lies along the whole supply chain, thus requiring solutions to react to different needs and stakeholders' actions.

Step 5: Establish the partnership: bridge the gaps and foster collaboration

With the results in hand, begin to form partnerships by bridging the gaps identified between different stakeholders. Recognize that each group—whether it's farmers, researchers, or policymakers—may have different ways of communicating or contributing. For instance, a farmer might prefer phone calls over online meetings, while researchers may focus on data-driven discussions.

- Foster collaboration by adapting to the needs and limitations of each stakeholder, ensuring all voices are heard and valued.
- Develop a shared vision for safe and sustainable food systems as the basis for change.
- Balance power structures that exist through knowledge, capacity and opportunity for advocacy, money- and funding flows
- Encourage the development of interconnected networks regionally, nationally, and globally to address solutions along the entire supply chain.

Tip: Be mindful of how different stakeholders engage. You may need to offer alternative forms of participation, such as engaging youth or marginalized groups in ways that meet their specific needs.

TOOL 3:

Guidelines for organizing and facilitating mirror groups

1) What is a Mirror Group?

A mirror group brings together organizations and initiatives that are not directly involved in a project or partnership but may be impacted by it and/or have valuable related experience to contribute. These mirror group participants learn about and reflect on the work happening in the project/partnership to provide useful input and recommendations to ensure that activities and decision-making are as inclusive and impactful as possible. After participating in a mirror group, participants may become more directly involved in project/partnership activities, when no conflict of interest arise.

2) Why are Mirror Groups needed?

Mirror groups help us:

- Include perspectives that are needed but missing.
- Recognize and reconcile different organizational backgrounds and agendas.
- Understand how to collaborate effectively.
- Share ideas, establish a common language, and agree on a common basis for advancing a systems approach to sustainable food system (SFS) transformation.

3) How to set up Mirror Groups

The FOODPathS project recommends nominating a group of 2 to 3 individuals, with support from a communications team to organize the mirror groups following the steps below:

Setting the scene:

Step 1: Develop a concept note

A concept note establishes a shared understanding for the purpose, organization, and facilitation of a mirror group. It ensures an efficient use of time and establishes roles and responsibilities. It clarifies how the mirror group connects to a project or partnership's objectives, the methodology for selecting mirror group participants, a timeline and expected outcomes. See Annex 1 for a Template.

1. Set objectives and a timeline for the mirror groups and for each meeting

- Clearly define the objectives for working with Mirror Groups, aligned with the project/partnership's aims, needs, and expected outcomes. Make sure meetings take place with adequate time to incorporate the input into final decisions or actions.
- Clearly define the objectives for each Mirror Group meeting and ensure the objectives guide the project/partnership closer to a solution to a challenge, help identify necessary changes for a more effective and inclusive partnership, and/or provide input at key points in time before final decisions are made and actions taken.

2. Identify relevant participants

- Identify participants from sectors relevant to your area of focus, such as government, civic society, research, private, and/or industry.
- Involve project partners in identifying potential participants
- Input them into a spreadsheet with additional information about the organization, type, and focus area. See Annex 2 for a template.

3. Be clear about what the project/partnership can offer participants

- Think about participants' needs and ways to facilitate their participation, especially if you are considering involving vulnerable and underrepresented groups. Are you able to provide financial honorariums? Organizational representation on a website? Travel support for in-person events.
- Be transparent and realistic about how you will be using the outcomes of the mirror group discussions.

4. Set a timeline

- The time needed for the organization of mirror groups from start to finish can vary. For FOODPathS, concept notes for each meeting were developed at least 2 months in advance and invitation rounds started 1.5 months prior to the event.
- Allow yourself a buffer of 1 month between sending out the invitations to your expected date to account for follow-ups, cancellations, and additional invitation rounds.

Step 2: Engage the project/partnership consortium

- Meeting with topic leads to understanding when and about what they could benefit from input from 'external' entities. Add this input into the concept note and 'run of show' (Annex 3).
- Request input for and review of the 'background' information pack that will be sent to participants (WHAT TO REFER TO??)
- Ask for suggestions for who to invite to the Mirror Group meetings/exchanges.

Step 3: Mirror group participant selection process

- Think about how many people you would like to involve, considering how many facilitators you have available and that breakout groups in meetings should have a maximum of 8 participants for the highest amount of participation. Look at the actors you have identified in step one and take a closer look at their vision, work, target audience, and engagement methods. Think about geography - where are they based?
- Develop criteria and establish a committee for participant screening.
- Find a good balance of actors to prioritize in the first round of invitations, and a list of suitable candidates for a second round.

Step 4: Invitation process

- Send your invitations early - in the context of FOODPathS, this was done 1.5 months prior - so that people can confirm attendance or reject the invitation.
- **Tip:** The FOODPathS Mirror Groups took place on Zoom. A registration link to the Zoom Call was sent in the initial invitation email, which helped track registrations in real-time, while also enabling participants to add the event directly to their calendars.

- Where possible, address organizational representatives directly by working with consortium/partners who have a direct connection to an entity you want to invite.
- To achieve a high and positive response rate, it is important to be clear in the invitation. Communicate clearly and transparently about how insights and opinions shared in the meetings will be used and what level of confidentiality is expected.

Step 5: Brief participants prior to the workshop

- Attach the background document providing an overview of the project, its aims and objectives, key topics and participation benefits.
- Prepare a detailed briefing package to send to participants once they confirm their attendance, explaining in greater detail the methodology, participation guidelines, and questions discussed.
- Conditions for Successful Mirror Group Meetings
- Set the right conditions for discussion and support processes with effective preparation and strategies by deciding (with input from the project/partnership consortium) what you would like input on, what questions to ask, and what methodology you will use. Make sure to provide definitions of terms that may vary across countries to ensure understanding.

Clarify Roles and Responsibilities

- Look within your consortium to see who can support in facilitating the mirror groups, either as facilitators or notetakers.
- Hold briefing meetings with relevant parties to update them on the envisioned methods, their roles and responsibilities. Clarify questions.
- Create a shared “Run of Show” Document outlining the agenda and responsibilities. See Annex 3 for a template.

Establish a Safer* Space

- Set ground rules to create a dynamic where participants feel heard, can listen and learn from one another free of their institutional mandates.
- Encourage participants to leave their titles at the door to foster an open dialogue.
- Start with icebreakers, have breakout groups, and make technical support available to help participants feel more at ease.
- Obtain consent from participants if the meeting is recorded and meeting minutes published with quotes.

Use tools that are intuitive and easy to use

- Advance access to resources and briefing materials
- Provide participants with the necessary resources two weeks in advance, including background information, preparatory materials and briefing packages.
- If you will be working in breakout groups focused on select topics, give participants information in advance.

Step 6: Time Management

- Manage time effectively during the meeting to ensure all topics are covered and discussions are productive.

Concluding activities

Step 7: Documenting the mirror group meeting (s)

- Provide notetakers with a Word document template to capture discussion points.
- Document discussions, decisions, and feedback thoroughly. Use various tools like meeting minutes, online collaborative tools (Miro boards, Google Docs, Mural etc.) recordings, and summary reports to capture the outcomes.

- Share the outcomes with all participants and stakeholders to ensure transparency and continuous improvement.

Step 8: Follow up with participants

- Encourage and welcome participants to share relevant new thoughts, ideas and criticism' that might have arisen after the event itself. This helps in continuously improving propositions and actions.
- Send out a feedback survey following the meeting to gather participants' impressions and suggestions for improvement.
- Once notes are consolidated, share outcomes with workshop participants, indicating how they will be used going forward.
- Integrate input back into the project.
- Share outcomes with your wider consortium and the public as appropriate. Share meeting minutes via email, upload them onto shared data platforms (e.g. Google or SharePoint), share relevant information via social media and publish summaries on the project/ partnership website.

Mirror Group Concept Note and Work Plan

Overview

Partners and Roles

- Organizers:
- Presenters:
- Tech and logistics:
- Breakout room facilitators and note-takers:
- Event host:

Concept Note

Context	
Objective	
Approach	
Mirror Group Participants	Spreadsheet of possible invitees
Participation Benefits	
Meeting Facilitation/ Methodology/Agenda	
Output	

Timeline	
Next Steps	

2. Selection and Invitation Process

Task	Description
Invitee Management	Spreadsheet
Selection Process	
Invitations	
Meeting Link	
Presentation	
Timeline of Invitation Process	
Next Steps	

Draft Invitation Email

Draft 1-Pager

Annex 2

[Mirror Group Participation list mapping template](#)

Annex 3

Mirror Group Run of Show template

[Length]

[Starting Time – Ending Time]

[Date, Year]

[Meeting Link]

Time (CET)	Agenda Item Responsible person	Description Note Taker	Logistics Responsible person
9:30 (10')	Welcome and Agenda Overview Responsible person		Share slides Responsible person

			Chat monitor Responsible person
9.40 (10')	Icebreaker Responsible person		Chat monitor Responsible person
9.50 (15')	Introduction to FOODPathS Responsible person		Share slides Responsible person Chat monitor Responsible person
10.05 (5')	Introduction to breakout room 1 Responsible person		Chat monitor Responsible person Assign breakout rooms Responsible person
Breakout Room 1 <i>Please download a copy of this notes template and send it to X (xxx@xxx.org) after the meeting.</i>			
10.10 (30')	Breakout Room 1 5' introduce each other 5' silent answer questions 5' add information to the sticky notes 15' discussion	1.	Facilitator/ Note Taker
		2.	Facilitator/ Note Taker
		3.	Facilitator/ Note Taker
		4.	Facilitator/ Note Taker
		5.	Facilitator/ Note Taker
Short Break of 5 Minutes			
Re-gather and share-back 1			
10.45 (20')	Report back to the whole group Facilitator		

11.05 (10')	Introduction to Breakout Room 2 Topic Responsible person		Share slides Responsible person Chat monitor Responsible person
Breakout Room 2 <i>Same break out groups as before</i>			
11.15 (25')	Breakout Room 2 Facilitators/ Notetakers	1.	Facilitator/ Note Taker
		2.	Facilitator/ Note Taker
		3.	Facilitator/ Note Taker
		4.	Facilitator/ Note Taker
		5.	Facilitator/ Note Taker
Re-gather and share-back 2			
11.40 (20')	Wrap Up Responsible person		Share slides Responsible person Chat monitor Responsible person

Breakout Rooms

Please download a copy of the meeting note template and modify your downloaded version and send us the notes after the meeting.

Topic	Questions	Facilitator	Notes

Please stay in the meeting room for a brief debrief.

Roles and Responsibilities

Role	Person Responsible
Moderator/Facilitation	
Zoom Logistics	
Time Keeper + Screen sharer	
Plenary Notes taker	
Plenary Chat Monitor	

TOOL 5: Case studies development

The Tool: Case studies development

The template has several key elements that are essential for describing a case study:

- The history of the case
- Its main characteristics
- The interactions between the actors
- The behavior of the actors

The word TEMPLATE:

1. One pager summary of the case with clarifying images (see also powerpoint 1-pager)
 - a. Short description in terms of why, what, who, how, when
 - b. Clarifying image(s) and description of the overall case concept/scheme
 - c. Presentation of main findings in the case
2. A written section on specified food system building blocks:
 - a. Playing field (i.e. the contextual setting in which a case evolves)

- b. Players (i.e. the actors that are involved (e.g. policy making institution, legislators, financiers, company, university, NGO, citizen collective, ...) in the FS case)
 - c. Pieces (the resources, products, services, procedures, documents, ... that are dealt with in the case; this also includes waste, by-products, GHG emissions, carbon storage in soils, expert opinions, charts, guidelines, etc.)
 - d. Moves (the variety of handlings of pieces, like production cycles, digestion, communicating, policy making, curricula, ...)
 - e. Rules / constraints / incentives (all measures that define the freedom/restrictions to play, like food laws, subsidies,..)
 - f. Outcomes (win – lose, the first dealing with sustainable outcomes; the second with unsustainable outcomes or negatively impacting sustainability)
 - g. Duration/time (the history – today – tomorrow evolution of the case)
3. A written section on interactions within and inter actors in systems:
- a. The actor's internal strength (i.e. the internal force and main assets of an actor (farmer, company, public institution, ...) that gives it stability / resilience, allowing to control its operations, hence related to its capacity to execute its core 'business')
 - b. The actor's capacity to adapt to a change, hence related to its flexibility to operate (e.g. recruiting temporary staff members, or adding other new resources or partners in case of targeting a new opportunity)
 - c. The interactions between actors, i.e. the interactions and interdependencies that allow cooperation & co-creation versus competition.
 - d. Common focus of interacting actors, i.e. the formulated joint ambitions of interacting actors.

1. The TEMPLATE in Powerpoint version

The powerpoint TEMPLATE is included below (note: a separate powerpoint file will be provided as well). This is the same format as presented at the workshop co-creation during the Kick-off meeting on the 29th of June 2022. However, it now also includes the option to add *some pictures, a somewhat more structured way of describing interactions between actors, and even some sustainability performance indicators of actors (their behavior)*.

Name of the food systems co-creation case / Country

One or two key features:

Status (starting, running, on-hold, stopped):

DESCRIPTION

History of co-creation between actors:

Which ambitions and objectives:

Evolution of their governance model and organisation:

What external input and output:

Photo banner (including country)

An illustration
(Product, service, organisation change, ...)

The seven Food System building blocks (like in a GAME):

Food context (playing field)	Food Actors (players)	Products (pieces)	Food handling actions (moves)	Boundary conditions (rules & incentives)	Results (outcomes regarding sustainability)	Timing of actions (duration)

FOOD ACTORS: what are their roles, how do they interact, and what are then their common objectives (max 3)

Actor's strength (what specific skills, or competences, or assets or are provided?)	Flexibility of actor (is an actor adapting to others in this case and how?)	Interactions between diverse actors (do actors form a cluster, network?)	Common focus as 'cluster' of actors (do actors jointly define a goal(s)?)	Joint objectives with other 'clusters / FS' (do clusters work with others?)

Some words about the sustainability behaviour of actors
(e.g. their willingness to take action, their new decision making processes to incorporate sustainability, their perceptions about their responsibility in the sustainability transition, their own impression about their level of impact (ratio benefits/trade-offs), ...)

.....

.....

.....

Main sources:

Contact person:

HorizonEurope CSA FOODPathS; WP

Funded by the European Union

Figure 4: The Template used for case studies

Finally it should be noted that to ensure the appropriate selection and analysis of cases (for further information on case studies, please read FOODPathS Deliverable D2.1), a list of keywords and criteria has been developed, drawing inspiration from those proposed by Prof. Silvia Scaramuzzi and her SCAR FS SWG Thematic Support Team at the University of Florence.

- i. Food systems
- ii. Food systems sustainability
- iii. Food systems approach
- iv. Food systems transition
- v. Food systems resilience
- vi. Food systems governance
- vii. Food systems research
- viii. Food systems innovation
- ix. Food systems education (and training)
- x. Food system policies
- xi. Food system funding

- xii. Food system network
- xiii. Food system analysis
- xiv. Food system living lab
- xv. Food system chart
- xvi. Food system procurement
- xvii. Food system communication

TOOL 7: Engaging research and education

Step 1: Mapping and identifying active institutions

The first step in building partnerships is identifying which institutions are already active in food system education, research, and practice. The goal is to map these institutions based on their engagement level, focus on sustainability, and areas of expertise.

- **Create a database** of educational institutions from kindergarten to universities engaged in food systems work. See Annex 4 for a template on mapping educational and research networks
- **Identify focus areas:** this can include food security, sustainability, urban agriculture, community engagement, etc.
- **Sustainability focus:** Highlight institutions with sustainability at the core of their mission or curriculum.
- **Conduct surveys or interviews** with key representatives from these institutions to understand their current and future initiatives.

Step 2: Conduct workshops to understand various roles and responsibilities of different institutions

One major challenge in food systems work is navigating the roles and responsibilities of various institutions. It is often unclear which organizations have jurisdiction over food system planning and implementation, leading to confusion and inefficiency.

Tip: In the FOODPathS workshops, various institutions were engaged in discussions about best practices and key drivers in SSFS education. The focus areas included: (1) student learning and outcomes, (2) pedagogy and learning approaches, (3) values and the hidden curriculum, and (4) quality standards and assurance. Additionally, participants explored barriers to effective SSFS education, such as financial constraints, institutional management issues, national and international policy frameworks, and the skills and capacities of both students and teachers, as well as time limitations.

Step 3: Balance theory and practice

Encourage universities to develop food systems courses that blend theory with fieldwork, internships, and service learning. These can include partnerships with local food organizations, urban farms, or government agencies.

Step 4: Amplify community-driven efforts

Strengthen the connection between educational institutions and community initiatives. Working with communities ensures that food system policies are relevant and address the needs of local residents.

- **Community-led research:**
- **Policy advocacy:** Work with local governments and member states to integrate community voices into food systems planning. Universities can use their research to support community advocacy efforts and help shape local food policy.

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Funded by
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